

Face-swapping based Data Augmentation for ID Document and Selfie Face Verification

Elmokhtar Mohamed Moussa¹, Ioannis Sarridis², Emmanouil Krasanakis²
Nathan Ramoly¹, Symeon Papadopoulos², Ahmad Montaser Awal¹, Lara Younes¹

¹ IDnow AI & ML Center of Excellence
Cesson-Sévigné, France

{elmokhtar.mohamed.moussa,nathan.ramoly,montaser.awal,lara.younes}@idnow.io

² Information Technologies Institute, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas
Thessaloniki, Greece

{gsarridis,maniospas,papadop}@iti.gr

Abstract

In this work, we focus on identity verification by matching selfies to identity (ID) documents depicting faces. When applied to this task, state-of-the-art deep face verification models tend to underperform due to lack of documents specific visual features in the public datasets, and suffer from skin tone biases due to representation imbalances of skin tone groups in training data. To address both issues, we introduce a framework that generates ID documents containing synthetic face images to augment training datasets. Specifically, we transform selfies into document-style images by combining style banks of document templates and face-swapping generative models. Experiments on a public and a proprietary real-world dataset reveal that fine-tuning state-of-the-art face verification models with the proposed methodology yields 7.96% improvement in verification accuracy, while requiring only 25% of the original training data. Furthermore, improvements occur across all skin tone groups, including darker skin tones; though it is notoriously hard to perform accurate verification for this group, we achieve more than 50% relative reduction in false acceptance and false rejection rate gaps w.r.t. lighter skin tones.

1. Introduction

Remote identity verification has largely expanded during the past few years and is now required by multiple services that follow a Know Your Customer (KYC) process.¹ In ad-

¹<https://www.biometricupdate.com/202302/biometrics-adoption-for-remote-identity-verification-expands-as-tech-demo-begins> 8/1/2025

Figure 1. Face verification challenges in matching ID documents images with selfies of the same person: (1a) to (1d) are photo ID faces; (1e) is a photo meeting conformity standards, and (1f) is a selfie in the wild used as the reference image. Euclidean distances d between the reference image and others is presented. Consent was obtained from the subject of the photos.

dition to automatically analyze the content of identity (ID) documents, remote verification systems also assert that individuals depicted in each document match the person interacting remotely, typically by capturing a selfie.

In this context, a face verification system compares the selfie image to the face depicted in the submitted document. However, face verification models that leverage deep learn-

ing often underperform when applied to images captured in uncontrolled settings [1,2,7]. This can be attributed to task-specific challenges that should be addressed. First, face verification datasets suffer from the disparity between the very high number of unique individuals and the only few images (typically 2-4) that are available for each of them. Second, the authentication of each individual relies on a single ID document image. This scarcity of selfie and identity image sets hinders the generalization ability of trained deep learning models.

Further difficulties may arise due to variations specific to ID document images that are demonstrated in Figure 1. To begin with, those images could have unique visual designs imposed by their issuing entities, such as authorities or institutions. Notably, face images on documents are often overlaid with unique security features (*e.g.* holograms) that can partially occlude important face landmarks (eye, cheek, *etc.*) hindering the recognizability of the face. Additionally, the skin tone of the individual plays a significant role, especially in grayscale ID documents. In some cases, the color transformations applied are not well calibrated for darker skin populations, resulting in poor contrast in the image and, in extreme cases, hardly distinguishable facial features (see Figure 1c), thus degrading verification accuracy for individuals with darker skin tones disproportionately.

The characteristics inherent to identity photos of faces are often absent from the public datasets commonly used for face verification tasks. This introduces a domain shift that hinders the performance of state-of-the-art face verification models. Figure 2 illustrates the impact of the domain shift—from regular face photos to ID documents photos—on the embedding space using the features derived by a specific model [30]. In Figure 2a, many selfie face embeddings from our target distribution (in blue) fall near the source face (faces from RFW [38]) embedding distribution (in gray). However, Figure 2b shows that many embeddings of ID documents faces (in green) are out of distribution and fall outside the source distribution.

To address the aforementioned challenges, we propose a framework for augmenting a training set of selfies by utilizing a style bank of unlabeled ID document images. This is achieved through the use of a face-swapping generative model [13] to transfer the selfie faces onto synthetic document-style images. We show that our generation framework effectively reduces annotation efforts and enables the training of more robust face verification models. In addition, we study the impact of our findings on real-world application data of face verification, with particular fairness considerations with respect to the skin tone sensitive attribute. We achieve an overall 7.96% relative improvement in verification accuracy while reducing false acceptance and false rejection biases by more than 50%.

(c) Private dataset embeddings distribution with respect to RFW dataset. The split of the dataset is done on the basis of the labeled skin color attribute in comparison to the ethnicity group in RFW dataset.

Figure 2. UMAP plot of AdaFace face embeddings [30] from RFW test set and our proprietary test dataset. (2a) and (2b) characterizes the out-of-distribution nature of our data, especially apparent for ID document face embeddings. (2c) is a plot based on the distribution of the dataset with respect to skin color for proprietary data and ethnicity in the RFW dataset.

2. Related work

ID document and selfie matching ID document-selfie matching introduces unique cross-domain challenges [6] that distinguish it from general face recognition tasks. These two domains exhibit differences in image characteristics. ID document photos are typically of lower resolution and quality due to embedded security features. In addition, while selfies are of higher resolution, they are subject to variations in pose, expression, and capture environment. To address these challenges, DocFace+ [32] employs sibling Face-ResNet networks [14] to project ID document and selfie images into a unified feature space. They employ an additive margin softmax loss function based on CosFace [35]. However, recent advancements, such as the quality-aware additive margin softmax loss [17, 26], offer improvements over CosFace by dynamically adjusting the

margin based on the quality of the input images. Zhu et al. [41] propose a three-stage training pipeline: pre-training on public face datasets, followed by fine-tuning for verification and large-scale classification on a private dataset of 2.5 million ID-selfie pairs. While effective, this approach relies heavily on access to an extensive amount of annotated data.

Biases in face recognition systems. Recent studies have highlighted biases in face recognition systems, particularly concerning demographic attributes such as ethno-racial groups, skin tone, gender, and age [9, 12, 21, 30, 37]. Regarding racial or skin tone bias, the literature indicates that face recognition systems tend to underperform for non-white individuals (or those with darker skin tones), even when these groups are equally represented in the training data [20, 30]. A similar pattern emerges with gender bias, i.e., face recognition systems trained on datasets that over-represent female subjects often perform better for males [3]. In terms of age-related bias, the primary performance issues arise with children’s faces [27] and image pairs featuring large age gaps [30]. To address these challenges, some approaches propose training frameworks aimed at improving fairness in face recognition. For example, several methods [36, 39, 40] suggest adapting angular loss functions, such as ArcFace [11] or AdaFace [17], to account for different margins across population groups. However, focusing on the composition and quality of training data is generally more effective than employing in-processing methods.

Data augmentations for face recognition. Data augmentation techniques play a critical role in improving face recognition performance by enhancing data diversity and robustness. Traditional photometric augmentations, such as color jittering, random cropping, and blurring [17], help models generalize better under varying conditions. Apart from photometric augmentations, the recent advancements in generative AI resulted in several approaches utilizing synthetic data for the face recognition task [25, 29]. For instance, DCFace [18] utilizes a Dual Condition Diffusion Model to generate high-quality synthetic face images of the same subject under different styles selected from a predefined real-world style bank. Furthermore, GANDifface [24] uses StyleGAN3 [16] to synthesize identities and then generates realistic intra-class variations. Similarly, Idiff-face [8] is based on conditional latent diffusion models for generating synthetic faces with realistic variations. These generative approaches can be used to address data scarcity, demographic biases and long-tailed distribution, contributing to more balanced and robust face recognition systems.

Face swapping. Face swapping refers to the process of replacing the identity of an individual in a target image

with a different identity from a source image. This process maintains the original attributes of the target, such as head pose, facial expressions, lighting, and background but preserves the identity of the source image. Face swapping has gained attention for its applications in privacy-preserving systems [15, 23] and image compositing [5]. Recent approaches leverage Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) for more realistic results. Models like *DeepFake*², *SimSwap* [10], *FaceShifter* [22] and *Inswapper*³ have set benchmarks in high-fidelity face swapping, with emphasis on identity preservation and visual realism.

In our work, we draw inspiration from the generation framework proposed by DCFace [18] for realistic domain adaptation and utilize a predefined style bank of ID document photos. For each selfie in the training set, we sample a style from the style bank and employ a face swap GAN to generate face images that preserve identity while remaining consistent with the ID document domain.

3. Proposed Approach

Figure 3. Overview of the proposed data augmentation framework. The framework (green box) uses a face verification (FV) backbone to identify the top- k ID styles candidates for each selfie and generates a new ID document-style images via a face swap GAN.

We propose a two-stage framework for face verification training dataset augmentation, as illustrated in Figure 3. The proposed approach uses a face verification backbone to identify similar target style candidates for each training face image. It then generates new ID document-style images using a face swap GAN. The resulting augmented training set is used to fine-tune a face verification model.

²<https://github.com/deepfakes/faceswap>

³<https://github.com/haofanwang/inswapper>

3.1. Problem statement

Face verification is a specific task within face recognition without the classification head [11, 31, 33, 34] aiming to determine whether a pair of face images ($\mathbf{I}_1, \mathbf{I}_2$) belong to the same identity (a bona fide pair) or to two different identities (an imposter pair). This is determined by measuring the similarity of their corresponding face embeddings in the latent space of the face recognition model. Let $g : \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 3} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ represent an embedding function, typically a deep neural network, that maps an input RGB image \mathbf{I} of dimensions $H \times W$ to a feature vector $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^d$. The embeddings of the two face images, normalized to unit norm, $\mathbf{z}_1 = \frac{g(\mathbf{I}_1)}{\|g(\mathbf{I}_1)\|_2}$ and $\mathbf{z}_2 = \frac{g(\mathbf{I}_2)}{\|g(\mathbf{I}_2)\|_2}$ are compared using the squared Euclidean distance:

$$d(\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2) = \|\mathbf{z}_1 - \mathbf{z}_2\|_2^2. \quad (1)$$

We formulate the verification decision as a binary classification problem:

$$g(\mathbf{I}_1, \mathbf{I}_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } d(\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2) \leq \tau, \\ 0 & \text{if } d(\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2) > \tau, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where τ is a distance threshold and $g(\mathbf{I}_1, \mathbf{I}_2)$ is the verification model.

3.2. Framework overview

Motivated by advances in synthetic face generation [18, 25] using GANs and their application on face analysis tasks, we use these models to generate diverse face images that help us capture the variations and complexities of ID document designs, thus alleviating the need for extensive ID document-selfie pairs collection and annotation. This approach could potentially bridge the domain shift gap, enhancing the robustness of face verification models by training on synthetic data that closely reflect the characteristics of ID document photos.

The proposed generation framework integrates a GAN face-swap model to enhance the diversity of the training dataset and improve the face verification model robustness. We define the ID document style bank as a collection of unlabeled ID document photos. This provides diverse target styles for face-swapping GANs. The framework includes the following stages:

1. *ID document style sampling*: To achieve a good quality face swap, it is crucial to have similar identities in the source and target images. Here, for each selfie from the training set, we sample its top- k similar images from the style bank, using their face embedding Euclidean distances. The embeddings are computed with the Adaface model from [30].

Figure 4. The first column contains the source faces from selfies, while the rows display the face swap results from *GHOST* and *Inswapper* side by side, respectively. The results are ranked from the most (green arrow) to the least similar (red arrow) templates in the style bank.

2. *Style transfer with face swap GAN*: Employing a pre-trained face swap GAN to generate synthetic ID document images by swapping each selfie from the training data to each of its corresponding top- k sampled styles.
3. *Face recognition model training*: The synthetically augmented dataset is then used to fine-tune a face recognition model, aiming to improve its generalization capabilities.

3.3. Style transfer with face swap GAN

We consider two face swap GANs: *GHOST* [13] and *Inswapper* to transfer a face from a selfie to a target ID document style while preserving the identity of the selfie’s face. *GHOST* [4] is based on *FaceShifter* [22], an occlusion-aware photo swap GAN. This is important, as other face swap GANs (SimSwap [10]) often ignore occlusions, which results in less realistic ID document photos missing key security features. Figure 4, illustrates the results of the two generation models.

4. Experiments

4.1. Datasets

We utilize a private proprietary dataset for face verification in the wild, consisting of annotated selfie and ID document image pairs, encompassing 60K images from 14K distinct identities. Additionally, the dataset contains manual annotations of individual skin tone using the *Fitzpatrick scale* [28]. Note that we consider skin tone as a sensitive attribute, as in practice there are often disparities in identity verification accuracy between darker- and lighter-skinned individuals (see experiments below).

Skin tone	# Imposters	# Bona fide
fitz12	78064	7575
fitz34	12853	1171
fitz56	31317	2895

Table 1. Private test set pairs distribution w.r.t skin tone.

Race	# Imposters	# Bona fide
African	6000	3000
Asian	6000	3000
Caucasian	6000	3000
Indian	6000	3000

Table 2. RFW test set pairs distribution w.r.t race.

Methods	ID preservation (%)	Distance
Inswapper	94.13	0.85
GHOST	91.68	1.08

Table 3. Quantitative assessment of the face swap models using pre-trained Adaface model from [30].

To reduce rater subjectivity, we group the skin tone scale into three categories: **fitz12** contains Fitz1 \rightarrow 2, **fitz34** contains Fitz3 \rightarrow 4, and **fitz56** contains Fitz5 \rightarrow 6. During the data collection process, we made an effort to select a balanced number of samples for each skin tone group. This ensured a more equitable representation across the dataset, helping to mitigate potential demographic biases.

For testing verification accuracy, we compile an identity disjoint private test set. We sample on average 10 random negative pairs (imposters) for every test individual within the same skin tone group (Table 1).

We also benchmark our results against the public face verification dataset RFW [38], evaluating both recognition accuracy and fairness on demographics across four racial-ethnic groups (see Table 2). It is important to mention that the current study addresses ethnicity indirectly through the skin color assessment. While the Asian group is included in the RFW dataset, this group is not represented in our dataset. The assessment for this group is not representative and the trained model may exhibit biases w.r.t. this population group. This will be studied in future work.

4.2. Training

AdaFace is chosen for its state-of-the-art performance in face verification. We train the model with a margin $m = 0.4$, a batch size of 256, and a learning rate of $5e - 3$ for 200 epochs. The training takes approximately 24 hours on a NVIDIA A40 GPU. For all of our experiments, the decision threshold τ (Equation (2)) is tuned to an overall target FAR = 0.5%.

4.3. Evaluation

To select between candidate GANs, we evaluate the quality of the generated face swaps with two metrics: the Identity Preservation Rate (True Acceptance Rate), which measures how well the swapped faces retain the source identity and the average Euclidean distance between the source and output swapped face.

To compare our framework with alternatives, we evaluate face verification with respect to both performance and bias mitigation metrics. In terms of performance, we report the False Rejection Rate (FRR) and the accuracy at a predetermined overall False Acceptance Rate (FAR) of FAR=0.5%.

We further assess predictive biases between sensitive at-

tributes, for which we use two key metrics provided by the FairBench library [19] to assess the disparate mistreatment of multiple-value sensitive groups: ΔFRR_{\max} represents the maximum difference in FRR across the assessed sub-groups (here skin color), and analogously ΔFAR_{\max} represents the maximum difference in FAR across those sub-groups.

5. Results

In Section 5.1 we compare the two candidate face swap GANs for style transfer, to opt for the one demonstrating better identity preservation capabilities. Then, in Section 5.2, we assess the performance of the models fine-tuned on augmented training sets using the proposed generation framework. This evaluation highlights improvements in terms of models’ accuracy and robustness for the selfie-to-ID document verification task, while showing enhancement in fairness for darker skin faces.

5.1. GAN selection for style transfer

To assess the quality of the generated data with the face swap GANs, we evaluate them using two metrics: Identity preservation rate and average Euclidean distance. Table 3 shows a quantitative comparison between the GHOST and *Inswapper* face-swapping models. The latter achieves face swaps that better preserve identity and is thus the recommended approach going forward. The comparison is made *on the training dataset*, as our goal is to use the models to augment these data.

5.2. Face recognition

Table 4 presents a comparison between baseline off-the-shelf face recognition (FR) models and fine-tuned models, both w/ and w/o the proposed augmentation strategy. The baseline model [30], trained on the BUPT-BALANCED [39] dataset, designed with demographic fairness considerations, underperforms when applied to ID document and selfie comparisons, as highlighted by its overall FRR of 11.03%. The model exhibits a clear bias against individuals with darker skin tones (fitz 56). This is reflected in a high FRR of 19.24% and a FAR of 1.10% for this group.

These results highlight the importance of fine-tuning models on the target selfie and ID document pairs dataset, as demonstrated in Table 4. Notably, fine-tuning the baseline model (without any augmentation) reduces the FRR significantly, showcasing the effectiveness of this adaptation step.

Model	Fine-tuned	Augmented	FAR (%)				FRR (%)			
			fitz12	fitz34	fitz56	overall	fitz12	fitz34	fitz56	overall
baseline	✗	✗	0.30	0.31	1.10	0.50	7.60	12.64	19.24	11.03
fine-tuned baseline	✓	✗	<u>0.41</u>	0.58	0.70	0.50	<u>3.42</u>	4.44	<u>7.50</u>	<u>4.55</u>
fine-tuned baseline + GHOST	✓	✓	0.42	0.51	<u>0.70</u>	0.50	5.11	6.23	9.43	6.33
fine-tuned baseline + Inswapper	✓	✓	0.43	<u>0.51</u>	0.67	0.50	2.84	4.10	6.98	3.98

Table 4. Face recognition results on our proprietary test set with τ optimized for FAR=0.5%. The baseline model is trained on the BUPT-BALANCED dataset. Best and second best are highlighted in bold and underlined respectively.

Figure 5. Comparison of FRR evolution for different training set sizes across skin tone groups, with and without the proposed augmentation framework.

The last two rows depict the results of our proposed generation framework with different configurations, showing that using the *Inswapper* face swap GAN instead of *GHOST* is advantageous due to the image generation quality of *Inswapper* model (as discussed in Section 5.1). In particular, using *Inswapper* in the proposed framework allows for an overall improvement of 0.57% of the FRR compared to the baseline fine-tuned model (i.e., without any augmentation).

Figure 5, illustrates the evolution of model performance as a function of the total number of identities in the training dataset w/ and w/o the proposed augmentation framework. At 0%, where no fine-tuning is performed, the pretrained baseline model [30] is plotted. When only a small percentage of identities (5%, 10%, or 25%) is used for fine-tuning, the benefits of the proposed augmentation framework are most evident, particularly for the dark skin demographic (*Fitzpatrick types 5 and 6*). Remarkably, with just 25% of the total training identities, the augmented model achieves performance comparable to that of the model fine-tuned on the full training set.

Table 5 summarizes the presented models chosen disparate mistreatment measures with respect to skin color. Our augmentation strategy and selected GAN achieve the highest accuracy at 95.52% while improving the mitigation,

exhibiting the lowest ΔFAR_{\max} (0.24), indicating the most balanced FARs across demographic groups. These results highlight the effectiveness of fine-tuning, particularly with the proposed augmentation strategy, in improving recognition accuracy while mitigating biases across skin color demographics by also improving accuracy for harder groups.

Model	Accuracy (%)	ΔFAR_{\max}	ΔFRR_{\max}
baseline	88.47	0.80	11.64
fine-tuned baseline	94.95	0.29	4.08
fine-tuned baseline + GHOST	93.17	0.28	4.32
fine-tuned baseline + Inswapper	95.52	0.24	4.14

Table 5. Fairness results on our private test set. The baseline model is trained on the BUPT-BALANCED dataset.

5.3. Discussion

The main requirement of for our approach to run is an extensive style bank to accommodate face swapping similarity constraints. One solution could be to explore usage of openly available ID document specimens as a style bank.

As shown in Table 6 the baseline model performance on the original verification task from RFW degrades after being fine-tuned specifically for the selfie-to-ID document verification task. This is expected behavior as fine-tuning causes the model to specialize more in the new task. Moreover, as we increase the number of ID document images using our augmentation strategy (last two rows), the model specializes even more on our use case, and its performance in the original task further declines. One readily observable dissimilarity between RFW and our dataset is that, in the latter, faces are expressionless and frontal to slightly tilted. Whereas RFW encompasses images captured in the wild with multiple facial expressions.

Considering the above insights, we plan to investigate training a unified model for face verification as part of future work. This model would aim to perform consistently across diverse scenarios, including ID document-to-selfie and in-the-wild face images matching. A potential direction to achieve this could involve generalizing the proposed framework to generate data that comprehensively represent multiple face verification scenarios. By incorporating such

Model	African	Asian	Caucasian	Indian
baseline	91.33	93.04	95.78	93.77
fine-tuned baseline	85.29	85.09	89.23	87.22
fine-tuned baseline + GHOST	79.57	77.02	83.39	81.30
fine-tuned baseline + Inswapper	81.90	78.02	84.73	83.83

Table 6. Accuracy (in %) results on RFW. The baseline model is trained on the BUPT-BALANCED dataset.

diverse data, the model could effectively address the challenges posed by variations in face verification tasks.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we showed that off-the-shelf verification models may struggle when applied to ID document portrait images due to the domain shift introducing occlusions, color transformations, and noisy real-world capture conditions. In particular, these models severely underperformed for minority groups such as people with dark skin (fitz56). We thus proposed usage of face swap generative models for adapting selfie images to ID document portraits. Preliminary exploration led to our use of Inswapper GAN for a realistic generation of document-style images while preserving individual identity.

Based on the above, we designed an augmentation framework that employs face swapping between selfie faces and an unlabeled style bank of ID document images. This approach significantly reduces the need for extensive collection and annotation of selfie-document pairs. Notably, using only a quarter of the training dataset classes, we achieve the same results as vanilla fine-tuning on the full training dataset. The proposed synthetic augmentation framework enhances the model’s robustness in the ID document verification domain while also improving accuracy for the dark-skin tone group.

Acknowledgment

This research work was funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe MAMMOth project, Grant Agreement ID: 101070285.

References

[1] Shivang Agarwal, Jyoti Chaudhary, Hard Savani, Shivam Sharma, Mayank Vatsa, Richa Singh, Shyam Prasad Adhikari, Sangeeth Reddy, Kshitij Agrawal, and Hemant Misra. Leveraging synthetic data and hard pair mining for selfie vs id face verification. In *2023 IEEE International Joint Conference on Biometrics (IJCB)*, pages 1–9, 2023. 2

[2] Vítor Albiero, Nisha Srinivas, Esteban Villalobos, Jorge Perez-Facuse, Roberto Rosenthal, Domingo Mery, Karl Ricanek, and Kevin W Bowyer. Identity document to selfie

face matching across adolescence. In *2020 IEEE International Joint Conference on Biometrics (IJCB)*, pages 1–9. IEEE, 2020. 2

[3] Vítor Albiero, Kai Zhang, and Kevin W Bowyer. How does gender balance in training data affect face recognition accuracy? In *IJCB. IEEE*, 2020. 3

[4] Sanoojan Baliah, Qinliang Lin, Shengcai Liao, Xiaodan Liang, and Muhammad Haris Khan. Realistic and efficient face swapping: A unified approach with diffusion models, 2024. accepted for publication WACV2025. 4

[5] Dmitri Bitouk, Neeraj Kumar, Samreen Dhillon, Peter Belhumeur, and Shree K Nayar. Face swapping: automatically replacing faces in photographs. In *ACM SIGGRAPH 2008 papers*, pages 1–8, 2008. 3

[6] Thirimachos Bourlai, Arun Ross, and Anil Jain. On matching digital face images against scanned passport photos. In *2009 First IEEE International Conference on Biometrics, Identity and Security (BIDS)*, pages 1–10, 2009. 2

[7] Thirimachos Bourlai, Arun Ross, and Anil K Jain. Restoring degraded face images: A case study in matching faxed, printed, and scanned photos. *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, 6(2):371–384, 2011. 2

[8] Fadi Boutros, Jonas Henry Grebe, Arjan Kuijper, and Naser Damer. Idiff-face: Synthetic-based face recognition through fuzzy identity-conditioned diffusion model. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 19650–19661, 2023. 3

[9] Joy Buolamwini and Timnit Gebru. Gender shades: Intersectional accuracy disparities in commercial gender classification. In *Proc. FAccT*. PMLR, 2018. 3

[10] Renwang Chen, Xuanhong Chen, Bingbing Ni, and Yanhao Ge. SimSwap: An Efficient Framework For High Fidelity Face Swapping. In *Proceedings of the 28th ACM International Conference on Multimedia, MM '20*, pages 2003–2011, New York, NY, USA, Oct. 2020. Association for Computing Machinery. 3, 4

[11] Jiankang Deng, Jia Guo, Niannan Xue, and Stefanos Zafeiriou. ArcFace: Additive Angular Margin Loss for Deep Face Recognition. In *2019 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 4685–4694, June 2019. 3, 4

[12] Raul Vicente Garcia, Lukasz Wandzik, Louisa Grabner, and Joerg Krueger. The harms of demographic bias in deep face recognition research. In *ICB. IEEE*, 2019. 3

[13] Alexander Groshev, Anastasia Maltseva, Daniil Chesakov, Andrey Kuznetsov, and Denis Dimitrov. Ghost—a new face swap approach for image and video domains. *IEEE Access*, 10:83452–83462, 2022. 2, 4

[14] Abul Hasnat, Julien Bohné, Jonathan Milgram, Stéphane Gentic, and Liming Chen. Deepvisage: Making face recognition simple yet with powerful generalization skills. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops*, pages 1682–1691, 2017. 2

[15] Håkon Hukkelås, Rudolf Mester, and Frank Lindseth. Deepprivacy: A generative adversarial network for face anonymization. In *International symposium on visual computing*, pages 565–578. Springer, 2019. 3

- [16] Tero Karras, Miika Aittala, Samuli Laine, Erik Härkönen, Janne Hellsten, Jaakko Lehtinen, and Timo Aila. Alias-free generative adversarial networks. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 34:852–863, 2021. [3](#)
- [17] Minchul Kim, Anil K. Jain, and Xiaoming Liu. AdaFace: Quality Adaptive Margin for Face Recognition. In *2022 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 18729–18738, New Orleans, LA, USA, June 2022. IEEE. [2](#), [3](#)
- [18] Minchul Kim, Feng Liu, Anil Jain, and Xiaoming Liu. DC-Face: Synthetic Face Generation With Dual Condition Diffusion Model. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 12715–12725, 2023. [3](#), [4](#)
- [19] Emmanouil Krasanakis and Symeon Papadopoulos. Towards Standardizing AI Bias Exploration. *Proceedings of the 1st Workshop on AI bias: Measurements, Mitigation, Explanation Strategies*, 2024. [5](#)
- [20] KS Krishnapriya, Vítor Albiero, Kushal Vangara, Michael C King, and Kevin W Bowyer. Issues related to face recognition accuracy varying based on race and skin tone. *IEEE Transactions on Technology and Society*, 1(1):8–20, 2020. [3](#)
- [21] David Leslie. Understanding bias in facial recognition technologies. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.07023*, 2020. [3](#)
- [22] Lingzhi Li, Jianmin Bao, Hao Yang, Dong Chen, and Fang Wen. Advancing High Fidelity Identity Swapping for Forgery Detection. In *2020 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 5073–5082, Seattle, WA, USA, June 2020. IEEE. [3](#), [4](#)
- [23] Sachit Mahajan, Ling-Jyh Chen, and Tzu-Chieh Tsai. Swaptip: A face swap application for privacy protection. In *2017 IEEE 31st international conference on advanced information networking and applications (AINA)*, pages 46–50. IEEE, 2017. [3](#)
- [24] Pietro Melzi, Christian Rathgeb, Ruben Tolosana, Ruben Vera-Rodriguez, Dominik Lawatsch, Florian Domin, and Maxim Schaubert. Gandifface: Controllable generation of synthetic datasets for face recognition with realistic variations. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 3086–3095, 2023. [3](#)
- [25] Pietro Melzi, Ruben Tolosana, Ruben Vera-Rodriguez, Minchul Kim, Christian Rathgeb, Xiaoming Liu, Ivan DeAndres-Tame, Aythami Morales, Julian Fierrez, Javier Ortega-Garcia, et al. FRCSyn-onGoing: Benchmarking and comprehensive evaluation of real and synthetic data to improve face recognition systems. *Information Fusion*, 107:102322, July 2024. [3](#), [4](#)
- [26] Qiang Meng, Shichao Zhao, Zhida Huang, and Feng Zhou. Magface: A universal representation for face recognition and quality assessment. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 14225–14234, 2021. [2](#)
- [27] Dana Michalski, Sau Yee Yiu, and Chris Malec. The impact of age and threshold variation on facial recognition algorithm performance using images of children. In *Proc. ICB*. IEEE, 2018. [3](#)
- [28] W. C. Quevedo Jr., T. B. Fitzpatrick, M. A. Pathak, and K. Jimbow. Role of light in human skin color variation. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology*, 43(3):393–408, 1975. [4](#)
- [29] Ángela Sánchez-Pérez, Enrique Mas-Candela, and Jorge Calvo-Zaragoza. Evaluating face recognition performance on synthetic data: A comprehensive analysis of methodologies and benchmarks. In *2024 IEEE International Joint Conference on Biometrics (IJCB)*, pages 1–10. IEEE, 2024. [3](#)
- [30] Ioannis Sarridis, Christos Koutlis, Symeon Papadopoulos, and Christos Diou. Towards Fair Face Verification: An In-depth Analysis of Demographic Biases. (arXiv:2307.10011), July 2023. [2](#), [3](#), [4](#), [5](#), [6](#)
- [31] Florian Schroff, Dmitry Kalenichenko, and James Philbin. FaceNet: A unified embedding for face recognition and clustering. In *2015 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 815–823, Boston, MA, USA, June 2015. IEEE. [4](#)
- [32] Yichun Shi and Anil K Jain. Docface+: Id document to selfie matching. *IEEE Transactions on Biometrics, Behavior, and Identity Science*, 1(1):56–67, 2019. [2](#)
- [33] Yi Sun, Yuheng Chen, Xiaogang Wang, and Xiaoou Tang. Deep learning face representation by joint identification-verification. In *Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems - Volume 2*, NIPS’14, pages 1988–1996, Cambridge, MA, USA, Dec. 2014. MIT Press. [4](#)
- [34] Yaniv Taigman, Ming Yang, Marc’Aurelio Ranzato, and Lior Wolf. DeepFace: Closing the Gap to Human-Level Performance in Face Verification. In *2014 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 1701–1708, June 2014. [4](#)
- [35] Hao Wang, Yitong Wang, Zheng Zhou, Xing Ji, Dihong Gong, Jingchao Zhou, Zhifeng Li, and Wei Liu. Cosface: Large margin cosine loss for deep face recognition. In *2018 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 5265–5274, 2018. [2](#)
- [36] Mei Wang and Weihong Deng. Mitigating bias in face recognition using skewness-aware reinforcement learning. In *Proc. CVPR*, 2020. [3](#)
- [37] Mei Wang and Weihong Deng. Deep face recognition: A survey. *Neurocomputing*, 429, 2021. [3](#)
- [38] Mei Wang, Weihong Deng, Jiani Hu, Xunqiang Tao, and Yaohai Huang. Racial Faces in the Wild: Reducing Racial Bias by Information Maximization Adaptation Network. In *2019 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, pages 692–702, Seoul, Korea (South), Oct. 2019. IEEE. [2](#), [5](#)
- [39] Mei Wang, Yaobin Zhang, and Weihong Deng. Meta balanced network for fair face recognition. *TPAMI*, 44(11), 2021. [3](#), [5](#)
- [40] Zhanjia Yang, Xiangping Zhu, Changyuan Jiang, Wenshuang Liu, and Linlin Shen. Ramface: race adaptive margin based face recognition for racial bias mitigation. In *IJCB*. IEEE, 2021. [3](#)
- [41] Xiangyu Zhu, Hao Liu, Zhen Lei, Hailin Shi, Fan Yang, Dong Yi, Guojun Qi, and Stan Z Li. Large-scale bisample learning on id versus spot face recognition. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 127:684–700, 2019. [3](#)